

Parametric Facial Landmark Detection Using Active Shape Models

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KEYWORDS

Facial Landmark Detection,
Active Shape Models (ASM),
Cascade Regressio,
Parametric Representation,
Face Recognition

ABSTRACT

Facial landmark detection plays a vital role in various applications, including face recognition and 3D face reconstruction. In this study, we introduce a parametric approach based on Active Shape Models (ASM) for facial landmark detection. Specifically, we encode landmark locations using ASM parameters and employ cascade regression to estimate these parameters. The final landmark positions are then derived from the ASM parameters. This parametric formulation offers a more compact and efficient representation compared to existing methods. Experimental results validate the effectiveness of our approach.

1. INTRODUCTION

The human face is a complex multidimensional structure that requires advanced computational techniques for accurate recognition. As the primary focus of social interaction, the face plays a crucial role in individual identity. Humans have an exceptional ability to recognize familiar faces, even after many years, despite variations caused by aging, facial hair, glasses, or changes in hairstyle. To mimic this capability, facial recognition algorithms extract and process facial features, continuously improving through modifications to existing models.

Facial recognition technology has a wide range of applications, including criminal identification, security systems, and identity verification. It is also widely used in online platforms, such as social networking sites and image-hosting services. In such systems, facial features are extracted, processed, and compared with a database of stored faces. If a match is found, the face is identified as known; otherwise, it is classified as unknown. In surveillance applications, unknown faces that appear multiple times can be stored for further analysis, making this technology particularly useful in law enforcement and security.

Face recognition techniques are generally categorized into two groups:

1. **Appearance-based methods** – These use holistic texture features applied to face images.
2. **Feature-based methods** – These rely on geometric facial features, such as the eyes, nose, and mouth, as well as the relationships between them.

The proposed technique focuses on encoding and decoding facial images, emphasizing both local and global facial features. Face recognition is a significant aspect of biometric technology, aiming to identify or verify individuals using 2D or 3D facial characteristics. A key component of this process is **facial landmark detection**, which involves identifying prominent facial features such as eye corners, the nose tip, and mouth corners. Accurate landmark detection is essential for tasks such as facial expression analysis, gaze estimation, and 3D face reconstruction.

Among early face recognition methods, **Eigenfaces** played a foundational role by projecting face images onto a lower-dimensional feature space. Other methods, including **elastic bunch graph matching** and **support vector machines**, have also contributed to advancements in the field. However, challenges persist due to factors such as facial expressions, pose variations, occlusions, and illumination changes, all of which can significantly impact recognition accuracy. Illumination variation, in particular, is a major factor affecting facial appearance, as light source direction influences shadows and intensity fluctuations. Addressing these variations is crucial for enhancing the robustness of face recognition systems.

The proposed approach extracts relevant facial features, encodes them, and compares them against a face database for classification as either known or unknown. While face recognition technology has significantly improved in recent years, challenges remain, particularly in uncontrolled environments with varying lighting conditions, poses, and aging effects. The objective of this work is to develop a robust model capable of distinguishing a target face from a large database while maintaining high accuracy under real-world variations. Unlike conventional methods, this approach is independent of factors such as lighting conditions, pose variations, and the presence of facial

accessories like glasses, ensuring more reliable recognition in diverse scenarios.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The **Active Shape Model (ASM)** is an algorithm based on the **Point Distribution Model (PDM)**, which represents geometric shapes of similar objects—such as human faces, hands, hearts, and lungs—using a set of key points (landmarks) arranged in a shape vector. ASM models facial landmarks as a deformable statistical structure and adjusts its parameters to fit the key points of a given facial image based on detected local features. Several feature detection methods can be incorporated into ASM, including **Boosted Haar Wavelets** [4], **Local Binary Patterns (LBP)** [5], and **Mutual Information** [6].

An alternative to these feature detection methods is the use of **regression techniques** for local searches. Unlike traditional classifiers in ASM, which learn a discriminative function between the local neighborhood and feature appearance, regressors aim to learn the relationship between local features and the displacement of landmark ground-truth locations. For instance, **Seise et al.** [7] employ a **Relevance Vector Machine (RVM)** regressor to update feature locations, while **Wimmer et al.** [8] use **Haar Wavelet features** to optimize an objective function that aligns with ground-truth locations.

Several studies have compared the performance of different feature detection methods and regression techniques. **Everingham et al.** [9] compared **Kernel Ridge Regression** with a **Bayesian Classifier**, concluding that a simple classifier performs better for eye detection. Similarly, **Cristinacce et al.** [10] demonstrated that local feature regression models offer improved localization accuracy and greater efficiency.

Other research efforts have focused on enhancing the **shape model** to improve detection accuracy. The original ASM represents face shapes using **Principal Component Analysis (PCA)**. **Zhou et al.** [11] projected facial shapes into a **tangent space** and applied **Bayesian inference** to estimate both shape and pose parameters. Recognizing that the regressed shape is a linear combination of training shapes, **Cao et al.** [12] introduced a constraint-based shape model that replaces PCA with a linear combination of training data. Due to its accuracy, speed, and robustness against

illumination variations, ASM has gained popularity, especially for **mobile device implementations** [13].

- **Cascade Regression-Based Methods**

Cascade regression-based approaches iteratively refine landmark positions by learning a regressor at each cascade level. These regressors map local features around the current key points to their ground-truth locations. The variation in cascade regression methods largely depends on the choice of **input features** and **regressors**.

- **Supervised Descent Method (SDM)** [3] and **Local Binary Features (LBF)** [14] employ linear regressors at each cascade level.
- **SDM** utilizes **SIFT features** related to face shape, whereas **LBF** extracts **sparse binarization features** using a **random forest regression model**.
- **Discriminative Response Map Fitting (DRMF)** [15] introduces a **parametric facial shape model**, incorporating **Support Vector Regression (SVR)** with **HOG features**.

Recently, **deep learning-based cascade regression frameworks** have achieved remarkable results. **Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DCNN)** [16] integrate **coarse-to-fine cascades** with **geometric refinement** to detect 68 facial landmarks. Instead of directly applying a deep network, the **Coarse-to-Fine Auto-encoder Networks (CFAN)** [17] approach stacks multiple **auto-encoder networks** to nonlinearly infer facial landmarks. **DeCaFA** [18] further enhances deep cascade architectures by incorporating **landmark-wise attention maps** and **intermediate supervisions** to improve landmark detection accuracy.

To address the challenge of **occluded landmarks**, **Wan et al.** [19] proposed a framework integrating a **deep regression module** with a **de-occlusion module**. However, deep learning-based approaches remain highly dependent on **large-scale training datasets** and are more prone to **overfitting**.

- **Proposed Approach**

In this work, we introduce a **parametric ASM-based approach** for facial landmark detection. Our method encodes landmark locations using **ASM parameters** and leverages **cascade regression** to estimate these parameters. Finally, the facial landmark locations are decoded from the estimated ASM parameters. This **compact representation** not only

enhances landmark location estimation but also mitigates overfitting issues present in deep learning-based methods.

3.PARAMETRIC APPROACH USING ACTIVE SHAPE MODELS FOR FACIAL LANDMARK DETECTION

We propose a new framework in the face recognition System by using Active Shape model (ASM). Initially we detect the face from the image. After that we extract the LBP feature. It is used to find the texture feature for the face image. The LBP operator assigned a label to every pixel of a gray level image. The label mapping to a pixel is affected by the relationship between this pixel and its eight neighbors. Active shape model (ASM) is a statistical model of the shape of objects which iteratively deform to fit to an example of the object in a new image. The shapes are constrained by the PDM (Point Distribution Model) Statistical Shape Model to vary only in ways seen in a training set of labeled examples. To locate a better position for each point one can look for strong edges, or a match to a statistical model of what is expected at the point. Then weighted matching will be applied between the input image and database images.

Figure 1: Proposed Model for Facial Landmark Detection

MODULES in the processing are given by

- Preprocessing
- Normalization
- Active shape model
- Feature Extraction
- Recognition

3.1 Module Description

Preprocessing

In noise removal process, initially we convert the image in gray. And then we filter the noise from the image. In Filtering we are applying Gaussian filtering to our input image. Gaussian filtering is often used to

remove the noise from the image. Here we used wiener2 function to our input image. **Gaussian filter** is windowed filter of linear class, by its nature is weighted mean. Gaussian filter is named after famous scientist Carl Gauss because weights in the filter calculated according to Gaussian distribution.

Normalization

Normalization is a process that changes the range of pixel intensity values. Illumination changes caused by light sources at arbitrary positions and intensities contribute to a significant amount of variability. To address this issue, we present a new method for performing image normalization. The method used to remove shadows and specularities from images. All the shadowed regions are grayed out to a uniform color, eliminating soft shadows and specularities and hence creating an illumination invariant signature of the original image.

Active Shape model

Active shape models (ASMs) are statistical models of the shape of objects which iteratively deform to fit to an example of the object in a new image. The shapes are constrained by the PDM (point distribution model) Statistical shape model to vary only in ways seen in a training set of labelled examples. The shape of an object is represented by a set of points (controlled by the shape model). The ASM algorithm aims to match the model to a new image. It works by alternating the following steps: Look in the image around each point for a better position for that point. Update the model parameters to best match to these new found positions.

Feature Extraction

Initially we separate the image as patches. For each patch of image, we apply the LBP (Local Binary Pattern). The LBP operator assigned a label to every pixel of a gray level image. The label mapping to a pixel is affected by the relationship between this pixel and its eight neighbors of the pixel. If we set the gray level image is I , and Z_0 is one pixel in this image. So we can define the operator as a function of Z_0 and its neighbors, Z_1, \dots, Z_8 . And it can be written as:

$$T = t(Z_0, Z_0-Z_1, Z_0-Z_2, \dots, Z_0-Z_8).$$

However, the LBP operator is not directly affected by the gray value of Z_0 , so we can redefine the function as following:

$$T = t(Z_0-Z_1, Z_0-Z_2, \dots, Z_0-Z_8).$$

To simplify the function and ignore the scaling of grey level, we use only the sign of each element instead of the exact value. So the operator function will become:

$$T = t(s(Z_0-Z_1), s(Z_0-Z_2), \dots, s(Z_0-Z_8)).$$

Where the $s(\cdot)$ is a binary function, defined as $s(x) = 1, x \geq 0; S(x) = 0$, otherwise.

Histogram features

An image histogram is a type of histogram that acts as a graphical representation of tonal distribution describes the distribution of various bright and dark tones with in an image. During the scanning or image editing stage tones can be redistributed lightening a dark image (or) darkening a bright image. This histogram plots the no. of pixels for each tonal value. by looking at the histogram for a specific image a person will be able to judge the entire tonal distribution.

Image histograms are present on many modern digital cameras. The horizontal axis of the graph represents the tonal variations and the vertical axis represents the no.of pixels in that particular tone. For this histogram we are assuming a discrete function $h(r_k) = n_k$ Here r_k is the k th gray level and n_k is the no. of pixels in the image at the gray level r_k .

Figure 2: Different Types of Histogram Images with Different Contrasts

Recognition

Here the recognition process is identified by the weighted matching. The Euclidean distance for LBP based histogram features is computed for the test feature with the database features. The similarity is identified between the features. Finally identified image is displayed.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Data Set

We have employed a set of images These images have been logically chosen by art historians in order to

address different tasks such as (a) to test the relation of an unmediated image of the subject, e.g., a death mask to a work of portrait art like a painting, (b) to analyze a number of portraits of different sitters by the same artist to model artist's style, (c) to verify if the identity of the ambiguous subject in a given image is same as that of a known subject in a reference image.

Identity Verification

In order to examine the validity of the chosen approach, we consider similarity scores of the test image with artworks known to depict persons different from the one depicted in reference image. We call these images as distracters. In cases where enough works of the same artist is not available, we consider similar works of other artists. If a test image indeed represents the same sitter as in the reference image, not only should its score with the reference image be modelled by the match distribution, but also its scores with distracter faces should be modelled by the non-match distribution. The results of the proposed system are shown below.

Selection of input image

Input image

Filtering

Normalization

Active Shape Model

Recognition

Advantages:

1. Security levels will be significantly improved.
2. The integration process is easy and flawless
3. High accuracy allows avoiding false identification
4. Facial Recognition System is fully automated
5. Time fraud will be excluded

Applications

1. Historical Persons Database
2. Politics
3. Education
4. Industrial
5. Security
6. Military

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Viola and M. Jones, "Rapid object detection using a boosted cascade of simple features," in Proceedings of the 2001 IEEE computer society conference on computer vision and pattern recognition. CVPR 2001, vol. 1. IEEE, 2001, pp. 1–I.
- [2] T. Ahonen, A. Hadid, and M. Pietikainen, "Face recognition with local " binary patterns," in European conference on computer vision. Springer, 2004, pp. 469–481.
- [3] N. D. Dowson and R. Bowden, "Simultaneous modeling and tracking (smat) of feature sets," in 2005 IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR'05), vol. 2. IEEE, 2005, pp. 99–105.
- [4] M. Seise, S. J. McKenna, I. W. Ricketts, and C. A. Wigderowitz, "Learning active shape models for bifurcating contours," IEEE transactions on medical imaging, vol. 26, no. 5, pp. 666–677, 2007.
- [5] M. Wimmer, F. Stulp, S. Tschechne, and B. Radig, "Learning robust objective functions for model fitting in image understanding applications." in BMVC, vol. 3, 2006, pp. 1159–1168.
- [6] M. Everingham and A. Zisserman, "Regression and classification approaches to eye localization in face images," in 7th International Conference on Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition (FGR06). IEEE, 2006, pp. 441–446.
- [7] D. Cristinacce and T. F. Cootes, "Boosted regression active shape models." in BMVC, vol. 2. Citeseer, 2007, pp. 880–889.
- [8] Y. Zhou and H.-j. Zhang, "Bayesian tangent shape model: Estimating shape and pose via bayesian inference," in IEEE Conf. on CVPR. Citeseer, 2003.
- [9] X. Cao, Y. Wei, F. Wen, and J. Sun, "Face alignment by explicit shape regression," International Journal of Computer Vision, vol. 107, no. 2, pp. 177–190, 2014.
- [10] Y.-H. Lee, C. G. Kim, Y. Kim, and T. K. Whangbo, "Facial landmarks detection using improved active shape model on android platform," Multimedia Tools and Applications, vol. 74, no. 20, pp. 8821–8830, 2015.
- [11] S. Ren, X. Cao, Y. Wei, and J. Sun, "Face alignment at 3000 fps via regressing local binary features," in Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2014, pp. 1685–1692.
- [12] A. Asthana, S. Zafeiriou, S. Cheng, and M. Pantic, "Robust discriminative response map fitting with constrained local models," in Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition, 2013, pp. 3444–3451.
- [13] E. Zhou, H. Fan, Z. Cao, Y. Jiang, and Q. Yin, "Extensive facial landmark localization with coarse-to-fine convolutional network cascade," in Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision workshops, 2013, pp. 386–391.
- [14] J. Zhang, S. Shan, M. Kan, and X. Chen, "Coarse-to-fine auto-encoder networks (cfan) for real-time face alignment," in European conference on computer vision. Springer, 2014, pp. 1–16.
- [15] A. Dapogny, K. Bailly, and M. Cord, "Decafa: deep convolutional cascade for face alignment in the wild," in Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision, 2019, pp. 6893–6901.
- [16] J. Wan, J. Li, Z. Lai, B. Du, and L. Zhang, "Robust face alignment by cascaded regression and de-occlusion," Neural Networks, vol. 123, pp. 261–272, 2020.
- [17] Potti, B., Subramanyam, M. V., & Prasad, K. S. (2013). A packet priority approach to mitigate starvation in wireless mesh network with multimedia traffic. International Journal of Computer Applications, 62(14).
- [18] Potti, B., Subramanyam, M. V., & Satya Prasad, K. (2016). Adopting Multi-radio Channel Approach in TCP Congestion Control Mechanisms to Mitigate Starvation in Wireless Mesh Networks. In Information Science and Applications (ICISA) 2016 (pp. 85-95). Springer Singapore.
- [19] Ravikiran, D. N., & Dethe, C. G. (2017). Fuzzy Rule Selection using LEACH Algorithm to Enhance Life Time in Wireless Sensor Networks. Advances in Wireless and Mobile Communications. ISSN, 0973-6972.
- [20] RaviKiran, D. N., Swetha, G., Annapurna, D. L., Teja, C. V., & Karthik, A. IoT Based Advanced Automatic Toll Collection and Vehicle Detection System
- [21] Polasi, P. K., Vellela, S. S., Narayana, J. L., Simon, J., Kapileswar, N., Prabu, R. T., & Rashed, A. N. Z. (2024). Data rates transmission, operation performance speed and figure of merit signature for various quadrature light sources under spectral and thermal effects. Journal of Optics, 1-11.

- [22] Thommandru, R. (2024). Cost-effective circularly polarized MIMO antenna for Wi-Fi applications. Cost-effective circularly polarized MIMO antenna for Wi-Fi applications (November 02, 2024).
- [23] RaviKiran, D. N., & Akhil, C. V. A Face Recognition Method for Security Applications in Smart Homes and Cities.
- [24] Haritha, K., Vellela, S. S., Vuyyuru, L. R., Malathi, N., & Dalavai, L. (2024, December). Distributed Blockchain-SDN Models for Robust Data Security in Cloud-Integrated IoT Networks. In 2024 3rd International Conference on Automation, Computing and Renewable Systems (ICACRS) (pp. 623-629). IEEE.
- [25] Ravikiran, D. N., & Dethe, C. G. (2018). Improvements in Routing Algorithms to Enhance Lifetime of Wireless Sensor Networks. International Journal of Computer Networks & Communications (IJCNC), 10(2), 23-32.
- [26] Potti, D. B., MV, D. S., & Kodati, D. S. P. (2015). Hybrid genetic optimization to mitigate starvation in wireless mesh networks. Hybrid Genetic Optimization to Mitigate Starvation in Wireless Mesh Networks, Indian Journal of Science and Technology, 8(23).
- [27] Thommandru, R. (2022). Survey on MIMO Antenna for 5G Applications.
- [28] Kumar, M. S., Vellela, S. S., Rao, G. R., Srinivas, B. R., Javvadi, S., SyamsundaraRao, T., & Kumar, K. K. (2024, September). An Interactive Healthcare Recommendation System Using Big Data Analytics. In 2024 3rd International Conference for Advancement in Technology (ICONAT) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [29] Nagaraju, C. H., Doss, B., Balamuralikrishna, P., Lakshmaiah, D., & Venu, I. (2023). Assimilation of Blockchain for Augmenting the Security and Coziness of an IoT-Based Smart Home. In Blockchain Technology for IoT and Wireless Communications (pp. 79-87). CRC Press.
- [30] Saravanakumar, R., Thommandru, R., Kumar, E. K., Al Ansari, M. S., Manage, P. S., & Muthuvel, S. K. (2024, April). Cross Scoop Fractal Antenna Design with Notch at 15 Degree for Emerging Applications at 5.2 GHz. In 2024 International Conference on Recent Advances in Electrical, Electronics, Ubiquitous Communication, and Computational Intelligence (RAEEUCCI) (pp. 1-7). IEEE.
- [31] Saravanakumar, R., Raja, A., Narayan, P., Rajesh, G., Vinoth, M., & Thommandru, R. (2024, September). Dual-Band Performance Enhancement of Square Wheel Antennas with FR4 Substrate for Sub 7GHz Applications. In 2024 International Conference on Advances in Computing Research on Science Engineering and Technology (ACROSET) (pp. 1-7). IEEE.
- [32] Reddy, N. V. R. S., Chitteti, C., Yesupadam, S., Desanamukula, V. S., Vellela, S. S., & Bommagani, N. J. (2023). Enhanced speckle noise reduction in breast cancer ultrasound imagery using a hybrid deep learning model. Ingénierie des Systèmes d'Information, 28(4), 1063-1071.
- [33] Devana, V. K. R., Beno, A., Alzaidi, M. S., Krishna, P. B. M., Divyamrutha, G., Awan, W. A., ... & Alathbah, M. (2024). A high bandwidth dimension ratio compact super wide band-flower slotted microstrip patch antenna for millimeter wireless applications. Heliyon, 10(1).
- [34] Saravanakumar, R., Ponnappalli, V. P., Thommandru, R., Khatak, S., HTP, M., & Thenmozhi, A. (2024, March). Analysis Circular Wave Guide Antenna for 5G Mid-Band Applications. In 2024 10th International Conference on Advanced Computing and Communication Systems (ICACCS) (Vol. 1, pp. 560-566). IEEE.
- [35] RaviKiran, D. N., Reddy, O. B., Mahalakshmi, R. S., Chaitanya, T. L., & Kumar, S. P. S. K. Secure Visual Data Processing: Image Encryption and Decryption through Reversible Logic Gates in VLSI Design.
- [36] Saidunagurunnisa, S., & Thommandru, R. (2019). Fire Fighter Robot With Night Vision Camera. International Journal of Research, 8.
- [37] Vullam, N., Roja, D., Rao, N., Vellela, S. S., Vuyyuru, L. R., & Kumar, K. K. (2023, December). An Enhancing Network Security: A Stacked Ensemble Intrusion Detection System for Effective Threat Mitigation. In 2023 3rd International Conference on Innovative Mechanisms for Industry Applications (ICIMIA) (pp. 1314-1321). IEEE.
- [38] Krishna, D., Kalyani, J., ThirumalaVenkatesh, Y., Balaji, V., Umamaheswari, T., & Srivalli, Y. (2024). An Efficient Low-Power Redundant-Transition-Free TSPC Dual-Edge-Triggering Flip-Flop using Single-Transistor-Clocked Buffer.